

ALHAGI HONEY-A MEDICINAL PLANT**Safarova Zakiya Teshaeвна¹,
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Abstract: the article contains materials on the medicinal properties of amber, biology, assembly of raw materials, use in folk medicine, honey.

Key words: amber, thorn, camel thorn, legumes, medicinal plant, honey plant.

Nature has generously endowed our country, plants grow here in all four seasons, the yield of plants is great. In addition to cultivated plants, our nature is also rich in wild plants, weeds of which we use in agriculture for feed, in folk medicine for treatment.

One of the weeds, fodder and medicinal plants is camel thorn. Camel thorn is a plant common in the steppe zones of Uzbekistan.

This plant from the genus Camel thorn (Latin *Alhagi*) belongs to the Legume family (Latin *Fabaceae*) or Moth family (Latin *Leguminosae/Papilionaceae*). This genus has seven (according to some sources, eight) species.

There are 5 species growing in Central Asia (including Uzbekistan): *Alhagi pseudalhagi* (M.Bieb.) Desv.ex Shap. - false yantak (false camel thorn), *Alhagi sparsifolia* Shap. - rare-leaved yantak (rare-leaved camel thorn), *Alhagi canescens* (Regel) V. Keller & Shap. - yantak grayish (camel's thorn grayish), *Alhagi kirghisorum* Schrenk. - Kirghiz yantak (Kirghiz camel thorn), *Alhagi persarum* Boiss. & Buhse. - Persian yantak (Persian camel thorn).

Yantak in another way-camel thorn is a root-springing perennial plant. Its powerful root goes 5-10 meters deep, initially it has a strictly vertical direction, but at a depth of at least 50 cm from the rhizome, numerous lateral roots begin to depart, having first a horizontal or oblique direction, and then, at some distance, deepening downwards, giving a vertical root and young shoots rushing upward.

The flowers of the camel thorn are moth-like, red, pink or purple. Camel Thorn Flower Formula - $H(5)L1+2+2T(9)+1P1$. The fruit of the plant is 4-5 seed thin bean. Seeds are small, smooth, black-brown or greenish.

In our republic and around the world, amber is a weed plant often found in deserts and semi-deserts of Asia and North Africa. It grows massively on the territory of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, Saratov and Volgograd regions, is often found in the Caucasus and Transcaucasia. Seven species of camel thorn are known, all of them are excellent honey plants of great importance for beekeeping.

On the territory of the Bukhara region up to 45°With and available moisture to the plant, growth is accelerated. Flowering begins in June and lasts for August. Reddish or pink flowers develop in the axils of the leaves. Nectar excretion is abundant. After a cool night on a hot day, you can see sweet "manna" on the leaves and stems.

From ancient amber was used in folk medicine. The medicinal raw material is camel thorn grass, sometimes roots can be used. Squeezing the juice in fresh form is drunk for gastrointestinal diseases.

A decoction of camel thorn and an infusion of it are used for the prevention and treatment of gastrointestinal disorders, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract caused by bacterial pathogens. Since yantak has an antibacterial property, like an antibiotic.

In folk medicine, its juice and infusions treat colitis, dysentery, inflammation of the colon and duodenum, stomach ulcer, inflammation of the gallbladder. A decoction of camel thorn, drunk on an empty stomach, acts as a laxative and diuretic.

In acute angina, with various inflammations of the oral cavity, an infusion is used for rinsing. Patients with purulent otitis are advised to bury a decoction of camel thorn in the ear, and those suffering from cervical erosion are advised to douche them.

There is a use of camel thorn as a diaphoretic, antipyretic for colds. Externally, a decoction or infusion of camel thorn is used as compresses for ulcers, eczema, gangrene, purulent skin lesions, wounds, burns and cuts. Baths with the plant are an effective remedy for rheumatism, arthritis, gout, joint pain, rickets. The benefits of camel thorn in the treatment of hemorrhoids are undeniable. Baths with a plant are also used for this disease.

Использованная литература:

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